

D7.5

Dashboard

Marketing Campaign

Report

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D7.5/Dashboard Marketing Campaign Report

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Abstract

This report outlines the planning, execution, and outcomes of the *Dashboard Marketing Campaign*, launched in Month 48 (August 2025) to enhance visibility, engagement, and adoption of the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard across diverse stakeholder groups. The campaign was strategically designed to promote the Dashboard as a key tool for supporting multi-hazard risk assessment, preparedness, and resilience planning. The campaign focused on LinkedIn as the main dissemination channel, guided by a pre-planned social media calendar to ensure consistent and targeted outreach. The campaign engaged scientists, policymakers, risk planners, and private sector actors, highlighting how the Dashboard supports data-driven decision-making and resilience planning. Complementary actions beyond the launch of an organic campaign on social media included a dedicated newsletter and a Communication Toolkit to facilitate consistent messaging and extend the campaign's reach. Together, these actions formed a coordinated, audience-focused communication effort designed to increase awareness, stimulate adoption, and strengthen stakeholder engagement. This helped position the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard as a valuable resource for building resilience and supporting informed, multi-risk decision-making.

Dissemination level of the document

- Public
- Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
- Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the European Commission Services)

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1. Introduction

The purpose of the Dashboard Marketing Campaign, launched in Month 48 (August 2025) by Arctik, was to increase awareness, visibility, and uptake of the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard, developed under Task 2.3 of Work Package 2, among key stakeholder groups. By promoting the Dashboard as an accessible, user-oriented entry point to MYRIAD-EU's harmonised framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, and systemic risk management, the campaign sought to foster active use of the tool by practitioners, policymakers, researchers, and private sector actors involved in disaster risk assessment and management, and resilience planning.

Guided by a pre-planned social media calendar, the campaign ran over 12 weeks and featured a total of 20 organic posts. Each post highlighted the Dashboard's benefits and applications, with messaging tailored to 4 main audience groups: researchers, policymakers, risk planners, and private sector actors. Two complementary communication products extended the reach of the campaign and ensured message coherence: a dedicated newsletter distributed to 703 subscribers within the MYRIAD-EU network, and a Communication Toolkit shared with 143 consortium and sister project partners. The toolkit included ready-to-use promotional materials (videos, visuals, and sample texts) enabling partners to amplify the campaign through their own channels.

2. Campaign Objectives and Strategy

As outlined in the Grant Agreement, the Dashboard Marketing Campaign was conceived as a multi-sector, multi-region activity aimed at promoting the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard as a one-stop data visualisation platform for visualising the multi-hazard and multi-risk tools and methods developed and applied in the project. Building on the knowledge and networks developed during the Pilots (in close collaboration with WP3), the campaign aimed to deliver targeted messaging along with supporting evidence for each stakeholder group.

Before launching the campaign, **Arctik developed a comprehensive campaign plan**, defining clear objectives and guiding principles for the implementation. The campaign objectives were designed to ensure that the Dashboard not only reached its target audiences but also stimulated active use and interest. Specifically, the campaign aimed to:

- **Develop compelling messages** to promote the Dashboard's adoption in decision-making across sectors and regions.
- **Ensure the Dashboard reaches its target audiences**, including government agencies, private sector actors, researchers, and risk planners.
- **Generate interest and encourage active use** of the Dashboard as a practical tool for multi-risk assessment and resilience planning.
- **Leverage communication channels** to increase visibility among harder-to-reach stakeholders and expand the Dashboard's reach beyond established networks.

The campaign identified four main stakeholder groups, each addressed through tailored messages to ensure maximum relevance, engagement, and practical applicability.

For **government and public agencies**, the communication approach highlighted the Dashboard's capacity to support policy design and multi-hazard preparedness, drawing on

tested tools and case studies from five European regions. The objective was to demonstrate how the Dashboard could inform disaster preparedness and management strategies across sectors and governance levels.

The **private sector** was targeted with content focusing on systemic risk management, business continuity, and the practical use of the Dashboard to identify and mitigate risks. Messages were designed to show how businesses operating in diverse sectors—such as insurance, tourism, and agriculture—can strengthen their resilience to interconnected hazards.

For the **scientific and research community**, the campaign underscored the Dashboard’s scientific foundations and pilot-tested framework for analysing systemic risks across multiple hazards and sectors. The goal was to encourage researchers and institutions to use the platform as a reference point for advancing knowledge and supporting evidence-based disaster-risk management and resilience planning.

Finally, messages addressed to **risk planners** focused on the Dashboard’s operational guidance, practical tools, and real-world case studies. By showcasing lessons from the MYRIAD-EU Pilot regions, the campaign aimed to illustrate how planners can apply the Dashboard to develop forward-looking, cross-sectoral risk management plans suited to complex and evolving challenges.

The table below (Table 1) summarises the four target audiences and the corresponding key messages developed to reach and engage them effectively.

Table 1: Audience and messaging identified for the Dashboard Marketing Campaign

Target Audience	Tailored Message
<p>1. Government & Public Agencies Decision-makers and policymakers at national, regional, and local levels</p>	<p><i>“Pilot-tested in five European regions, the Dashboard provides actionable tools and case studies to help policymakers at all levels design policies for multi-hazard-risk preparedness and disaster risk management plans across sectors.”</i></p>
<p>2. Private Sector CEOs, insurance companies, hotel managers, farmers, and other sector actors</p>	<p><i>“The MYRIAD-EU Dashboard offers the private sector actionable insights to identify and reduce systemic risks, helping businesses maintain continuity in the face of multi-hazard risk challenges.”</i></p>
<p>3. Science & Research Researchers, academics, and institutions</p>	<p><i>“The MYRIAD-EU Dashboard provides researchers with a scientifically grounded, pilot-tested framework for analysing systemic risks across multiple hazards and sectors that can enhance your research.”</i></p>
<p>4. Risk Planners Planners involved in disaster risk management</p>	<p><i>“With practical tools, guidance and tried-and-tested case studies from pilot regions across Europe, the Dashboard empowers risk planners to develop actionable, forward-looking disaster risk management plans, ensuring readiness for diverse, interconnected, and evolving risks.”</i></p>

3. Communication Outputs

The campaign adopted a multi-channel communication strategy designed to effectively reach and engage the identified target audiences.

The Dashboard Marketing Campaign featured four main communication outputs:

- **A 12-week organic social media campaign** implemented on LinkedIn, consisting of 20 posts that highlighted the Dashboard’s functionalities, applications, and benefits. Each post was tailored to one of the four target audiences and scheduled

according to a predefined social media calendar to ensure consistency and strategic timing of dissemination.

- **A dedicated newsletter** distributed to 703 subscribers within the MYRIAD-EU community, aimed at reinforcing engagement and encouraging users to explore the Dashboard.
- **A Communication Toolkit** disseminated to 143 consortium and sister project partners, providing ready-to-use promotional materials such as visuals, short texts, and videos. The toolkit enabled partners to amplify the campaign and ensure consistent messaging across multiple communication channels.
- **A series of five challenge-based videos**, each showcasing one of the MYRIAD-EU pilot regions (the North Sea, Veneto, Scandinavia, Canary Islands, and Danube). The videos introduce key regional challenges and demonstrate how the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard supports stakeholders and practitioners in resilience and risk management. The scripts were co-developed together with pilot leads to ensure accuracy and relevance, whereas the video production was carried out by Arctic.

Through the combination of strategic messaging, audience segmentation, and coordinated multi-channel dissemination, the Dashboard Marketing Campaign effectively translated the Grant Agreement commitments into tangible actions that maximised awareness, promoted adoption, and strengthened stakeholder engagement.

3.1 Social Media Campaign

The first component of the Dashboard Marketing Campaign was the development and implementation of the social media campaign. Although the grant agreement initially included provisions for a paid campaign, the consortium agreed to pursue an organic, community-driven approach instead. An ‘organic’ social media campaign refers to outreach that grows naturally through unpaid posts, community interaction, and audience sharing, rather than through paid advertising. This strategy aims to amplify impact through authentic peer-to-peer engagement and by leveraging the strong online community cultivated over time to ensure broad and meaningful stakeholder participation.

Between September and December 2025, a 12-week organic campaign was implemented on LinkedIn, considered the most effective platform to reach professional and institutional audiences relevant to the Dashboard. The campaign aimed to increase visibility and promote adoption of the Dashboard across different stakeholder groups. First, a detailed social media calendar was developed to strategically plan and schedule 20 posts over the campaign period, ensuring a consistent flow of content aligned with key project milestones. A variety of media formats accompanied the posts, including short explanatory videos, screenshots showcasing the Dashboard’s functionalities, and visual templates aligned with the MYRIAD-EU brand identity. The campaign focused on developing compelling, audience-specific messages that encouraged Dashboard use in decision-making and generated active engagement. The figure below presents the key objectives of the Dashboard Campaign Plan in a clear, color-coded format. This color scheme is consistently applied in the social media calendar shown below to ensure visual alignment between objectives and campaign activities.

Figure 1: Key objectives of the Dashboard Marketing Campaign

Posts were tailored to four main audience groups (scientists and researchers, policymakers, risk planners, and businesses) with messages designed to reflect their professional priorities and needs. The content calendar featured all major components of the Dashboard: the MYRIAD-EU framework, the storylines approach, and several associated resources such as the Serious Game, the Terminology Handbook, and the Disaster Risk Gateway. It also spotlighted the tools and methods developed within the project, including the MYRIAD-EU software for multi-risk scenario analysis and the Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways (DAPP) approach for multi-risk policymaking. Together, these elements presented a coherent narrative illustrating how the Dashboard and its supporting tools contribute to more integrated, evidence-based, and resilient risk management across Europe.

Posts were scheduled and monitored using the Meltwater platform, which facilitated social media management and analytics tracking throughout the campaign. Between September 9 and December 9, the campaign posts collectively generated approximately 15,520 impressions and 375 reactions.

Highlights

Data for 9/9/2025 - 12/9/2025

15,520

Impressions

▲ 115.4%

375

Reactions

▲ 162.2%

10

Comments

▲ 900%

7

Reposts

▲ 40%

Figure 2: Engagement performance of the social media campaign. Data collected from LinkedIn Analytics.

Moreover, from September to December, the MYRIAD-EU LinkedIn account gained 72 new followers - an increase of 105% compared to the previous period - resulting in an overall follower growth of around 4.5%. These results demonstrate strong audience interest in visual and practical content, confirming LinkedIn as an effective platform for engaging professional stakeholders.

Follower highlights 📊

1,644
Total followers

72
New followers in the last 92 days
▲105.7%

Figure 3: Follower highlights of the social media campaign. (Data collected from LinkedIn Analytics).

Posts combining videos or visual banners with direct links to project outputs tend to perform best, achieving on average up to twice the engagement of static visuals.

Figure 4: Examples of social media posts published on MYRIAD-EU LinkedIn account.

3.2 Newsletter

As part of the Dashboard marketing campaign, a dedicated MYRIAD-EU newsletter was produced and distributed to 703 existing subscribers. The issue achieved an open rate of approximately 41.5 % and a click-through rate of 7.30%.

Figure 5: Open-rate and click through rate results of MYRIAD-EU's newsletter. Data collected from Campaign Monitor.

Engagement data taken from Campaign Monitor indicated that links directing readers to the Dashboard landing page and the “Storyline for multi-risk decision-making” attracted the highest number of clicks, confirming strong audience interest in the digital platform and its interactive tools.

Top links Full report

Link	Clicks
Link to web-based version of this email	60
https://dashboard.myriadproject.eu/	50
https://dashboard.myriadproject.eu/storylines-for-...	25
https://www.myriadproject.eu/	24
https://bridging-the-silos.myriadproject.eu/	23

Figure 6: Summary of most-clicked links in MYRIAD-EU’s newsletter. (Data collected from Campaign Monitor).

The newsletter marked a key moment in the project’s final phase, bridging reflection on recent achievements with a forward-looking call to action for Dashboard adoption. It opened by announcing the launch of the Dashboard marketing campaign in September 2025 and inviting readers to explore how the platform consolidates MYRIAD-EU’s scientific outputs into a single, user-friendly interface. The newsletter also highlighted recent project milestones, including the development of the “Bridging the Silos” serious game, and the publication of the storylines repository. A dedicated “ECR Corner” celebrated Early Career Researchers’ contributions, while short updates on sister projects, news, and upcoming events showcased the project’s broader collaborations. Overall, the newsletter effectively combined reflection, storytelling, and actionable information to drive continued interest in the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard. Its tone balanced technical insight with accessibility, successfully positioning the Dashboard as a practical, collaborative tool for scientists, policymakers, planners, and private-sector actors across Europe.

3.3 Communication Toolkit

The MYRIAD-EU Communication Toolkit was developed and distributed to 143 recipients, including consortium partners and sister project collaborators, to facilitate consistent, engaging, and effective dissemination of the Dashboard and its outputs.

The toolkit included a range of ready-to-use materials, such as a web article to launch the campaign, a short text suitable for project partners’ newsletters, and four social media posts featuring two videos, showcasing both the Dashboard interface and case studies from the pilot regions. These resources were designed to be adaptable across different communication channels and audiences, providing both narrative and visual content that could be easily incorporated into partners’ outreach strategies. The toolkit was designed and developed by Arctik to provide partners with clear, consistent messaging and visually engaging materials, ensuring coherent communication and enhancing the Dashboard’s reach and impact. It enables partners to amplify the Dashboard’s visibility, showcase its practical applications, and engage a wider audience with tools that strengthen resilience to multi-hazard risks.

PARATUS project featured Arctik’s video teaser of the Dashboard Marketing Campaign in its LinkedIn and X channel. SYNERGIES project also featured Arctik’s short text in their newsletter, in [November’s](#) episode.

Figure 7: Examples of two sister projects featuring MYRIAD-EU's toolkit materials.

3.4 Challenge-based videos

As part of the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard's organic marketing campaign, Arctik produced a series of five challenge-based videos, each focusing on one of the project's pilot regions: the North Sea, Veneto, Scandinavia, the Canary Islands, and the Danube. The videos were conceived as an engaging communication output to showcase how the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard can support stakeholders and practitioners in understanding and managing multi-hazard risks.

Each video introduces a real-world multi-hazard scenario relevant to its pilot region and illustrates how MYRIAD-EU research, tools, and approaches have been applied to address these complex challenges. This storytelling format was chosen to enhance accessibility for non-specialist audiences, bridging the gap between scientific research and practical implementation. The scripts were co-developed with the respective pilot leads to ensure technical accuracy, regional relevance, and consistent messaging across all outputs. Video production was coordinated by Arctik, which also supported the scriptwriting process, ensured the alignment of tone and visual identity with project communication guidelines, and oversaw the full production workflow.

The final videos were published on the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard website (<https://dashboard.myriadproject.eu/pilots>), and promoted through the MYRIAD-EU LinkedIn page as part of the project's organic communication strategy.

4. Conclusion

The Dashboard Marketing Campaign represented a coordinated, multi-channel effort that underscored MYRIAD-EU's commitment to ensuring its tools and methodologies deliver real-world impact, strengthening resilience and advancing multi-risk management across Europe and beyond.

During the Dashboard marketing campaign, the web traffic to the MYRIAD-EU Dashboard website saw a significant boost.

The site recorded **567 visits** (+102.5%), **1181 pageviews** (+73.4%), **30 downloads** (+233.3%), and **225 outlinks** (+82.9%) compared to the previous period, demonstrating increased user interaction and interest in the Dashboard's content.

Visits Overview

Figure 8: Overview of MYRIAD-EU Dashboard website's visits over campaign. (Data collected from Matomo).

Looking ahead, despite the MYRIAD-EU project marking its end as of December 2025, the Dashboard will remain online for at least five years after the project's completion, ensuring ongoing access to its tools, resources, and guidance.